

Characterization and Conformational Studies of a Novel Trinitro Steroid using 2D-NMR†

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Conformational analysis of nitro substituted 4-en-3-one steroids has been further investigated using high resolution 2D-NMR techniques. An attempt on the preparation of 6 β -nitrocholest-4-en-3-one resulted in a new trinitro steroid, 2,2,6 β -trinitrocholest-4-en-3-one. These compounds have been characterized using COSY, HETCOR, NOESY experiments and the probable pathways to these products have been discussed.

There has been a considerable interest in the conformation and conformational flexibility of 4-en-3-one steroids¹. The endocrinological importance of a number of natural and synthetic 6-substituted steroid hormones makes their stereochemistry even more interesting. Having confirmed the A-ring conformation in certain polybrominated cholest-4-en-3-ones², we thought it to be worthwhile preparing and studying the conformation of 6-nitrocholest-4-en-3-ones which also have an electron-withdrawing bulky substituent at 6-position. Also for such compounds assignments based only on low resolution NMR have been made. An attempt on the preparation of these nitrosteroids led to a new trinitro steroid, 2,2,6 β -trinitrocholest-4-en-3-one (**3**) whose structure and conformation were determined by using 2D-NMR techniques, like COSY, HETCOR, DQF-COSY, NOESY and 2D-J RESOLVED spectroscopy and NOEDS. The probable pathway to hitherto unreported product has also been discussed. Conformational analysis of the two nitro steroids has been done with the application of 2D-NMR methods which has further been supported by computer aided molecular modeling. Total ¹H and ¹³C resonances of the trinitro steroid have been assigned.

Various methods of synthesis of 6-nitro substituted steroidal 4-en-3-ones are available in the literature. Bowers *et al.*³ have synthesised 6 β -nitrocholest-4-en-3-one (**5**) by nitration of 3 β -acetoxycholest-5-ene with fuming nitric acid. The resulting 3 β -acetoxy-6 β -nitrocholest-5-ene was subjected to alkaline hydrolysis followed by chromic acid oxidation to get the desired product. Alternatively, it was prepared by nitration of enol-acetate of cholest-4-en-3-one with fuming nitric acid followed by alkaline hydrolysis⁴. The nitro compound was also obtained in a good yield by slow reaction of 3 β -acetoxycholest-5-ene with nitrosyl chloride in ether, followed by oxidation and dehydrohalogenation with HCl-aq.MeOH⁵⁻⁷. Fieser's modification⁵⁻⁷, utilizing fuming nitric acid in ether solution, was reported to give good yield of 6-nitro derivative of 3 β -acetoxycholest-5-ene on a

small scale. Rowland⁸ prepared 3 β -acetoxy-6-nitrocholest-5-ene by treatment of 3 β -acetoxycholest-5-ene in 1 : 1 mixture of conc.HNO₃/ether with potassium nitrite at 5° followed by rapid work-up.

Tori and Kuriyama⁹ have discussed long range shielding effects of the nitro group in 6 β -nitrotestosterone and its acetate on the basis of poorly resolved ¹H NMR spectra. They observed the NMR spectra of 6 α -nitrotestosterone, 6 β -nitrotestosterone and its acetate to examine changes in the chemical shifts of 10-CH₃ groups and C-4 protons due to introduction of the C-6 nitro groups. Configurations of the C-6 nitro groups in the epimers were ascertained from the fact that signals of C-4 and C-6 protons in 6 α -nitrotestosterone appeared as a doublet (*J* 2.0 Hz) and an octet (*J* 12.3, 4.7 and 2.0 Hz) respectively, whereas those in 6 β -nitrotestosterone appeared as a singlet and a quartet (*J* 4.6 and 2.0 Hz) respectively. The 10-CH₃ in 6 β -nitrotestosterone and its acetate was more shielded than that in cholest-4-en-3-one, whereas in 6 α -nitrotestosterone it is less shielded. This was explained by strong shielding effect of magnetic anisotropy of the nitro group, arising due to hindered rotation of the C-6 β and C-6 α nitro groups around the C(6)-N bond. Conformations similar to these were also adopted by the C-6 nitro groups in 6 α - and 6 β -nitrocholest-4-en-3-ones⁹.

Results and Discussion

Enol acetate **2** on treatment with fuming nitric acid in dry ether at -15°, yielded compound **3** (Scheme 2) after triturating the worked up reaction mixture with hexane. Attempts on its chromatographic purification on either silica or alumina led to its decomposition. Compound **3** showed a major (98%) single peak in HPLC reverse phase ODS column with eluant 10% H₂O in MeOH, together with a minor impurity. Reproducible results were obtained by repeating the reaction sequence under identical conditions. This compound was completely analyzed by 2D-NMR techniques, like

†Dedicated to Professor Sukh Dev on the occasion of his 75th. birth anniversary.

For structure 6, all ^{13}C NMR signals could be assigned except the quarternary resonance at 114.9 ppm, similarly C-2 was the only unassigned carbon left. The rearranged steroid structure possesses a carbonyl group at C-2. Since the resonance at 114.9 ppm is untenable for the carbonyl carbon in the proposed rearranged structure 6, hence this structure is ruled out.

Literature reports ^{13}C resonances of *gem*-dinitro carbon resonances for alicyclic compounds at 104–119 ppm¹⁸. Therefore, it can be deduced that two nitro groups are present at C-2 and the product can be identified as 2,2,6 β -trinitrocholest-4-en-3-one (3).

Computation with extended Karplus equation given by Colucci *et al.*¹⁰ with vicinal couplings 4.8 and 1.7 Hz, for 6 α -7 α and 6 α -7 β , yielded dihedral angles of 31.4° and 61.3° respectively. Any twisted conformation of the B-ring is expected to furnish coupling constants of higher order as in the case of polybrominated 4-en-3-one steroids². Also, the twist conformation of ring-B would make the 6 β -NO₂ group lie further apart from the C-10 methyl letting it experience reduced long-range shielding effect, if at all any, than the observed. The observed NOESY connectivity between H-4 and H-6 α suggests a slightly twisted conformation for ring-B, wherein H-4 and H-6 are proximate to each other in space. Construction of molecular models with calculated dihedral angles has suggested that B-ring is partially twisted in compound 3. The energy minimized structure of 3 shows that ring-A exists in a normal half-chair conformation with 2 β -NO₂ in equatorial and 2 α -NO₂ in the axial position. A slight distortion is brought about by the presence of olefinic group at C-4. Likewise, ring-B was also found to be distorted slightly and the 19-methyl and 6 β -nitro groups are poised almost parallel to each other.

The complete assignments of ^{13}C NMR spectra and partial assignment of ^1H NMR resonances of compound 5 were done by concerted application of COSY and HETCOR. Stereochemistry of the C-6 nitro group of compound 5 (Scheme 3) was confirmed to be β on the basis of the observed shielding of C-10 methyl (δ 1.11 ppm) by 0.07 ppm when compared to unsubstituted cholest-4-en-3-one. H-6 α resonates at δ 4.84 ppm (dd). This forms the X-part of the 'ABX' spin system. From the COSY connectivities, H-7 α and H-7 β were found to resonate at 1.40 and 2.72 ppm respectively. First order analysis of this spin system yielded the vicinal couplings $^3J_{(6\alpha,7\beta)}$ 5.1 and $^3J_{(6\alpha,7\alpha)}$ 1.5 Hz. Calculation of dihedral angles corresponding to these coupling constants with extended Karplus equation by Colucci *et al.*¹⁰ yielded dihedral angles of 30.8° and 64.0° 6 α -7 α and 6 α -7 β respectively. Had ring-B been completely twisted, it would have removed 10-CH₃ from the shielding cone of

Scheme 3. Synthesis of 6 β -nitrocholest-4-en-3-one (5).

C-6 nitro group, thereby causing it to resonate in a region more downfield than the observed. Conformation of B-ring was found to be partially twisted chair, with C-10 methyl experiencing the shielding effect of C-6 β -nitro group. The 10-methyl appears at δ 1.11 ppm which is slightly more deshielded than that in 6 β -nitrotestosterone where it appears at δ 1.05 ppm⁹. Comparison of coupling constants $J_{(6\alpha,7\alpha)}$ and $J_{(6\alpha,7\beta)}$ in 6 β -nitrocholest-4-en-3-one with those in 6 β -nitrotestosterone (4.6 and 2.0 Hz)⁹ and the corresponding dihedral angles derived showed that the B-ring in 6 β -nitrocholest-4-en-3-one is slightly more twisted exercising more shielding effect on C-4 olefinic proton (δ 6.08 ppm) in 6 β -nitrocholest-4-en-3-one than that in 6 β -nitrotestosterone⁹. This observation may be of stereochemical interest from the point view of a probable conformational transmission effect of the side-chain or the hydroxy at C-17 position, on ring-B. The proton corresponding to the relatively upfield signal at δ 2.54 ppm (ddd) showed a connectivity with the proton signal at δ 2.44 ppm and both these protons showed connectivities with two other protons in the upfield region in the COSY spectrum. The HETCOR spectrum confirmed these correlations. The above observations clearly indicate that these protons form an AA'BB' four spin system of A-ring in this molecule. A multiplet due to one of the C-2 protons at δ 2.58 was well resolved to make the first order analysis possible. The analysis yielded a geminal coupling constant $^2J_{(2\alpha,2\beta)}$ 17.12 Hz and two vicinal coupling

constants 3J 14.72 and 4.94 Hz. The extended Karplus equation¹⁰ with these vicinal couplings yielded the corresponding dihedral angles of 178° and 44.9° respectively. The calculated dihedral angle of 178° and coupling as high as 14.72 Hz can easily be conceived to arise from the diaxial protons at C-1 and C-2. Hence, the proton at δ 2.54 can be H-2 β of a normal or H-2 α of an inverted conformation. The geminal coupling observed is $^2J_{(2\alpha,2\beta)}$ 17.12 Hz suggesting that C-3 carbonyl bisects the angle H-C2-H¹⁸ which is possible only if A-ring adopts normal conformation. A sofa conformation is known to decrease the value of $^3J_{(1\alpha,2\beta)}$ as a result of decrease in the dihedral angle to an order of ca 172°. A-ring, therefore, can not adopt 1 α -sofa conformation.

Construction of molecular models has revealed that any inversion of A-ring flips C-10 methyl more towards B-ring. This would increase the van der Waals repulsions between the substituents at the 1,3-diaxial positions. These repulsions would minimize only if ring-B twists more completely as observed in the case of tribromocholest-4-en-3-one and dibromodiosgenone². But the observed vicinal coupling for H-6 α reveals that B-ring is not completely twisted. Moreover, inversion of the ring is likely to diminish shielding effect of the nitro at C-6 on the C-10 methyl, since the latter does not fall in the shielding cone of the nitro group in this conformation. These arguments clearly demonstrate that ring-A can only adopt normal 1 α , 2 β -half-chair conformation which is further supported by the computer aided molecular modeling studies. The observation of A-ring normal conformation of 6 β -nitrocholest-4-en-3-one further corroborates the fact that the nature of substituent at C-6 β position does not affect the A-ring geometry. Incredibly, *gem*-dinitro substitution at C-2 position in A-ring does not show any distortions and allows the ring to adopt a normal half-chair conformation.

Experimental

M.ps. are uncorrected. ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded on Bruker AM 500 and Varian VXR 300S spectrometers (with digital resolution 0.16 Hz). The spectra were referenced with tetramethylsilane as 0.0 ppm for ^1H NMR and the central line of CDCl_3 was set to 77.0 ppm for ^{13}C NMR. ^1H - ^1H COSY experiments were performed in absolute intensity mode on a Varian VXR 300S spectrometer with 256 t_1 increments and data size 512 W for acquisition. Homonuclear phase sensitive NOESY experiments were performed on a Varian VXR 300S spectrometer with $\pi - t_1 - \pi - \tau_m - \pi$ - FID pulse sequence with mixing time of 1 s and relaxation delay of 1.5 s. NOEDS studies were performed on a Bruker AM 500 spectrometer using DANTE pulse sequence. HETCOR experiments were per-

TABLE 1- ^1H AND ^{13}C NMR (δ) ASSIGNMENTS FOR COMPOUNDS 3 AND 5

	Compd. 3		Compd. 5	
	^{13}C	^1H	^{13}C	^1H
1	43.8	3.21(α) 3.11(β)	1	36.9 2.08(β) 1.74(α)
2	114.9	-	2	35.5 2.54(α) 2.44(β)
3	176.7	-	3	198.9 -
4	129.8	6.47	4	133.2 6.08
5	159.8	-	5	157.8 -
6	85.4	4.94(α)	6	86.5 4.84(α)
7	33.8	2.82(β) 1.45(α)	7	33.6 2.72(β) 1.40(α)
8	30.6	1.83(α)	8	30.7 1.85(β)
9	54.1	1.10(α)	9	52.6 0.94(α)
10	39.8	-	10	38.6 -
11	20.9	1.46(α,β)	11	21.1 1.09(α,β)
12	40.0	2.10(α)	12	39.2 1.38(α OR β)
13	42.5	-	13	42.3 -
14	55.4	1.09(α)	14	55.7 1.06(α)
15	23.8	1.62(β) 1.32(α)	15	23.6 -
16	28.0	1.89(β) 1.32(α)	16	27.9 1.49(α OR β)
17	56.0	1.08(α)	17	55.8 1.06(α)
18	12.1	0.73	18	11.9 0.73
19	18.6	1.02	19	17.9 1.11
20	35.6	1.39	20	33.9 1.12
21	18.6	0.92(α)	21	18.5 0.91(α)
22	36.1	1.34 1.20	22	36.2 -
23	23.8	1.32	23	23.8 -
24	39.5	1.10	24	39.2 1.31 1.03
25	28.0	1.52	25	27.6 1.46
26	22.5	0.86	26	22.6 0.86
27	22.8	0.88	27	22.9 0.88

formed on a Bruker AM 500 spectrometer with 256 data points in F_1 dimensions and 512 data points in F_2 dimension with zero filling on F_1 . Phase sensitive DQF-COSY and 2D-J resolved spectra were obtained on a Bruker AM 500 spectrometer with 256 W data size in F_1 dimension. The FIDs were Fourier transformed onto 1K \times 1K data matrix. Sine bell window function was used. The FAB mass studies were performed with a VGZAB-HF mass spectrometer using ion source of standard VG Analytical Inc., system equipped with a saddle field gun. Neon was used as the beam with accelerating voltage of 8 kV.

HPLC experiments were performed on a DuPont 8800 Instrument series using Reverse Phase ODS column with

eluant 10% H₂O in MeOH.

2,2,6β-Trinitrocholest-4-en-3-one (3) : Fuming HNO₃ (10 ml) was added for 30 min to a solution of enol acetate 2 (1 g) in dry ether (50 ml) with stirring at -10°. The mixture, after the addition, was further stirred for 2 h at 0°. It was then poured over ice-water and the product extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed with 5% NaHCO₃ till the alkaline solution just turned brown. Then it was washed several times with water and dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and concentrated *in vacuo*. The gummy residue obtained was triturated with hexane to obtain a white amorphous powder which was crystallized from ether-light petroleum to yield compound 3 (0.13 g), m.p. 190–92° (Found : C, 62.82; H, 8.10; N, 8.41. C₂₇H₄₁O₇N₃ calcd. for : C, 62.41; H, 7.95; N, 8.09%); λ_{max} (CHCl₃) 234 nm (log ε = 4.133); ν_{max} (KBr) 1710 and 1702 (C=O), 1620 (C=C), 1585, 1565 and 1555, 1365 cm⁻¹ (NO₂); m/z 520.3154 [M⁺]; ¹H and ¹³C NMR in Table 1.

Attempts to further purify the solid obtained resulted in the decomposition of the product.

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References

1. K. TORI, T. TOMITA, HITAZAKI, M. NARISIDA and W. NAGATA, *Chem. Pharm. Bull. (Tokyo)*, 1963, **11**, 956.
2. R. SRIDHARAN, U. R. DESAI, R. M. RAO and G. K. TRIVEDI, *Steroids*, 1993, **58**, 170.
3. A. BOWERS, M. B. SANCHEZ and H. J. RINGOLD, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, **81**, 3702.
4. A. BOWERS, L. C. IBANEZ and H. J. RINGOLD, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, **81**, 3707.
5. M. DAVIS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 2830.
6. W. A. HARRISON, S. EWART, R. H. JONES G. D. MAEKINS and P. A. WILKINSON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 3210.
7. C. E. ANAGNOSTOPOULOS and L. F. FIESER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 532.
8. A. T. ROWLAND, *Steroids*, 1975, **26**, 251.
9. K. TORI and K. KURIYAMA, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1964, 3939.
10. W. J. COLUCCI, S. J. JUNGK and R. D. GANDOUR, *Mag. Reson. Chem.*, 1985, **23**, 335.
11. J. ROMER, D. SCHELLER and G. GROSSMANN, *Mag. Reson. Chem.*, 1987, **25**, 135.
12. M. BARBER, R. S. BORDOLI, R. D. SEDWICK and A. N. TYLER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1981, 325.
13. M. BARBER, R. S. BORDOLI, R. D. SEDWICK and A. N. TYLER, *Nature*, 1981, **293**, 270.
14. C. R. ECK and B. GREEN, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1972, 537.
15. C. R. NARAYANAN, M. S. PARKER and M. S. WADIA, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1970, 4703.
16. A. HASSNER and J. LARKIN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **85**, 2181.
17. H. SUGINOME and Y. KUROKAWA, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1989, **54**, 5945.
18. D. A. CICHRA and H. G. ADOLPH, *Synthesis*, 1983, 830.
19. M. BARFIELD and D. M. GRANT, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **85**, 1899; *Magn. Reson. Chem.*, 1996, **34**, 740.